

VALKYRIES

D1.24 Impact Creation Report M24

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1. Executive Summary

VALKYRIES develops, integrates and demonstrates capabilities for enabling immediate and coordinated emergency response including search and rescue, security and health, in scenarios of natural/provoked catastrophes with multiple victims, with special application in cases in which several regions or countries are affected and hence greater interoperability being required.

As it is well understood the communication and dissemination in VALKYRIES plays a pivotal role. At month six (M6) the consortium released the Communication and Dissemination Strategy (D1.9) where the overall C&D strategy was drawn, planning its evaluation in a series of deliverables in M12 and M24 to track the impact generated by the consortium endeavours towards the accomplishment of the C&D goals. In this context, the present document drives the final effort to identify relevant lines of work which realization generate a positive impact in the performance indicators defined in D1.9. This deliverable is thus aimed on sharing the consortium vision towards the forwarding direction the C&D strategy is taking, which is presented in the form of reported joint and individual actions carried out by the VALKYRIES partners up to the current stage of the project, accounting dissemination and communication activities undertaken during the first year of the project as well.

Among the performed actions, the website reorganization has been possible with active participation of the consortium members, raising the importance of a strong web presence across the time. This online presence is intrinsically bound to the social media platforms, so that the consortium underpinned the basis for measuring analytics reflecting the impact of such platforms within the audience. In addition, external visibility has been pushed forward by the release of scientific publications framed in the research lines coped by VALKYRIES, as well as informative publications targeted to EMS practitioners. Furthermore, general-purposed communications broadcasted on the media in the form of press releases has been accounted in this report as their impact on the general audience is far more reaching. The liaison preliminary efforts conclude the tracked activities of this report, opening room to the next steps planned by the consortium members.

This deliverable corresponds to M13 – M24 reporting period. M1-M12 results can be found on D1.10. New contact has been highlighted in yellow for easy review.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Impact Creation Report M24

Deliverable Id: D1.24

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D1.24

Name of lead participant: Indra (IND)

Name of Contributors: All partners

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Linked project Work Package: WP1 - Project Management and Communication

Linked project tasks: T1.3 - Consultation Strategy and Liaison with European/national authorities / T1.4 - Dissemination strategy

Action: Design

Status: First Release (M13 – M24 reporting period)

Document Layout: VALKYRIES official template

Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions.

Deliverable D1.24 is framed into the project tasks T1.3 and T1.4, having the purpose to report the undertaken efforts to generate impact on the communication & dissemination strategy. The reported actions considered here are accounted in the reporting period from M13 to M24 of the project, as several partners' undergone efforts to disseminate their involvement in VALKYRIES among different audiences. Actions from M1 to M12 can be found on D1.10.

3. Document and Project Scope

3.1. Project Overview

The increasing frequency and intensity of natural and human-made disasters [1]- [2] requires policies aimed at tackling these risks through preventive, preparedness, response and recovery actions. Increasing the resilience of infrastructures, ecosystems and society in EU is an important strand of disaster risk management work.

It is from this need that VALKYRIES was born, a project co-financed by the European Union (EU) under the framework of the H2020 program. It is within the field of security, specifically in disaster-resilient societies under the topic *Pre-normative research and demonstration for disaster-resilient societies: First aids vehicles deployment, training, maintenance, logistic and remote centralized coordination means*.

The project will develop a methodology for tracking and analysing the needs for standardisation and harmonisation as regards the tools for supporting EU disaster resiliency. Specifically, it will develop, integrate and demonstrate capabilities for enabling immediate and coordinated emergency response, including for search and rescue, security and health, in scenarios of natural/provoked catastrophes with multiple victims, with special application in cases in several regions or countries.

In order to develop the project, a multidisciplinary consortium has been created with key partners from industry (large companies and SMEs), universities, research centres and end users, which jointly have defined a series of work streams and international and cross-sectorial use cases that give the project great value.

3.2. Document Structure

The document is organized as follows:

Section 1 presents the executive summary of the deliverable content.

Section 2 summarizes identifying information about the deliverable

Section 3 introduces the document and project scope.

Section 4 gives an overview on the communication activities carried out during the reporting period and the current status of the VALKYRIES' online presence.

Section 5 gives an overview on the dissemination activities carried out during the reporting period.

Section 6 reports the status of the liaison actions carried out with related EU projects.

Section 7 closes the document with the conclusions.

3.3. Requirements traceability matrix

Description of the requirements can be found in D2.1 and D2.7. The table below presents the requirements concerning Task T1.4.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Evidence
REQ_BASE_T 1.4_1	N/A	All	D1.10 D1.24	REQUIRED	All accomplished as expected. Information about Workshops/plenary can be found in www.valkyries-h2020.eu
REQ_BASE_T 1.4_2	N/A	All	-	REQUIRED	All the scientific contributions are accessible via www.valkyries-h2020.eu/Scientific_Publications.html
REQ_BASE_T 1.4_3	N/A	All	-	REQUIRED	Public documents are uploaded into the Zenodo platform to guarantee open access. https://zenodo.org/communities/val/?page=1&size=20
REQ_BASE_T 1.4_4	N/A	All	-	REQUIRED	All scientific contribution come with an Acknowledgement and EC logo All the scientific contributions links are accessible via www.valkyries-h2020.eu/Scientific_Publications.html
REQ_BASE_T 1.4_5	N/A	All	-	REQUIRED	The official web of the project contains a disclaimer that reflects that the disseminations results only reflects the author view.
REQ_BASE_T 1.4_6	N/A	All	-	RECOMMENDED	That information is accessible via www.valkyries-h2020.eu
REQ_BASE_T 1.4_7	N/A	All	-	RECOMMENDED	That information is accessible via www.valkyries-h2020.eu www.linkedin.com/company/valkyries-h2020 and https://twitter.com/ValkyriesH2020
REQ_BASE_T 1.4_8	N/A	All	D1.9	RECOMMENDED	Graphic line and template can be consulted via D1.9
REQ_BASE_T 1.4_9	N/A	All	D1.9	RECOMMENDED	NA. The D1.9 reflects de Definition of a unified communication strategy grounded on Key Performance Indicators
REQ_BASE_T 1.4_10	N/A	All	D1.9	REQUIRED	D1.9 available
REQ_BASE_T 1.4_11	N/A	All	D1.10 D1.24	REQUIRED	Information in D1.10 (M12) and D1.24 (M24)
REQ_BASE_T 1.4_12	N/A	All	D1.10 D1.24	RECOMMENDED	Information in D1.10 (M12) and D1.24 (M24)
REQ_COM_T 1.4_1	N/A	All	D1.9	OPTIONAL	Some actions like participating in scientific workshops (ARES) among partners

Table 1 – Requirements traceability matrix T1.4

4. Report on Communication

This section will provide an overview of the progress made during the second year of project in the communication activities of the VALKYRIES Project.

In M6, *D1.9 Communication and Dissemination Strategies* was delivered, where the Consortium's partners have included their individual and joint communication and dissemination plans, as well as the main activities to be carried out between M1-M12 and the detected activities, conferences and high impact journals for next year. In order to measure the progress and the success of these activities, a series of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were defined in D1.9 and the following have already been fulfilled or are in progress, as can be seen in Table 2.

Communication KPIs				
Activity	Description	Expected impact	KPIs	Progress Status
Design logo and presentation templates	Professional logo. Professional presentation template to be used by partners.	Visual identity and branding of the project; unified experience for the targeted audience.	Logo and templates available in professional quality by M2.	100%
Project fact sheet	Double-sided A4 page containing basic information on the project.	Provision of instant information about the project.	500+ readers reached.	100%
Project press releases	Showcase the progress and the results	Inform stakeholders, increase awareness and disseminate information	5+ Press releases per year	100%
Project newsletters	Showcase the progress and the results	Inform stakeholders, increase awareness and disseminate information	2+ newsletters per years	100%
Project website	A website, providing information about the project, the demos and the results to target audiences.	Main online information point; communication of project news, events results; liaisons with other initiatives, projects through links.	An average of 500+ visitors per year.	100%
Social Media channels	Regular sharing of news on activities and results as well as interaction with target audiences via social media.	Increasing visibility to stakeholders; direct communication mechanism between social media users and Consortium.	500+ followers on Twitter/LinkedIn	100%
			100+ tweets on Twitter	100%
			100+ Posts on LinkedIn.	100%
Joint events, round tables	Events co-organized with targeted stakeholders or where VALKYRIES will be invited to present its work and vision.	Information exchange and dissemination; increase awareness.	500+ participants reached in total over 24 months	100%
White papers	Posters/banners to present the project's concept; Flyers with general project information; ad-hoc information at selected events.	Communication of results and information provision at events; ad-hoc diffusion of information based on	2,000+ readers reached via printed and electronic copies.	100%

Communication KPIs				
Activity	Description	Expected impact	KPIs	Progress Status
		identified opportunities.		
Demonstration, show cases, exhibitions	Events where VALKYRIES will communicate its results through demonstrations.	Attraction of target audiences and making them aware of the VALKYRIES solutions' benefits.	2,000+ visitors reached in total over 24 months	100%

Table 2 - Progress in Communication KPIs

The activities performed in the reporting period covering M13 to M24 are described in the following subsections.

4.1. Website

4.1.1. Website Structure

The VALKYRIES website is accessible from M1 of the project so pushing forward the project's online presence among the general audience. Since the first period M1-M12, while maintaining the general structure of the website, new sections has been added. **Scientific Publications**, where the project started to publish links to all the scientific papers that have been produced in Valkyries, and **Tools**, which contains a set of tools that have been developed during the project and have been used during the different Use Cases. The current reorganized sitemap is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – VALKYRIES' website current structure. New sections in orange.

The current look of the website, which has been improved following a consultation during the last period, can be shown on Figure 2. A new feed links to social networks Twitter/X, and LinkedIn have been added to the front page.

Figure 2 – VALKYRIES' website main page

The purpose of each website section is better explained in Table 3.

Menu	Description
The project	Presents the VALKYRIES highlights along with the project objectives. The three submenus' contents have been rewritten with more engaging takeaways, explaining the project work streams (KARA, HERJA, EIR) associated with WP4, 5 and 6, respectively, the SIGRUN reference integration and the four use cases that will take place at the end of the project.
Consortium	Despite the improvement in presenting information from the consortium partners, the External Advisory Board members are presented.
Dissemination	Awareness of the public dissemination activities of VALKYRIES will impact positively at widening the visibility of the project in terms of communication and dissemination outcomes among the target stakeholders. This section is composed of three submenus for categorizing dissemination information : publications and participation in events, and the new Scientific Publications
Resources	This section makes room for additional categories purposed to provide visitors further sources of information including News, the project Newsletters and some Demo resources in order to get feedback for the audience and showcase interactive material

Menu	Description
Tools	The Valkyries project has a set of tools developed by the different partners covering several operational services identified in the system architecture. This section includes a description of each of the tools developed in the project.
Contact us	VALKYRIES contact information remains offering an official email account to address any type of inquiries or comments for the general audience, as well as a direct access to the project Twitter and LinkedIn profiles.

Table 3 – Website tabs

4.1.2. Updates

The most relevant updates on the website were performed during the first period M1-M12. In that period, the project website was created and published (<https://www.valkyries-h2020.eu>) and all the changes that reflected in D1.10.

During the reporting period a total of 2 updates have been made in the VALKYRIES's website on M18, M19, and M21. These updates include:

- Typos correction
- New Social Networks feeds on the front page
- New events carried out on the "Events" tab
- New publications carried out on the "Publications" tab
- New section Scientific Publications, and an item for each paper/proceeding.
- News that have taken place on the "News" tab
- Newsletters - Issues 3 and 4 on the "Newsletters" tab
- New "Tools" tab, that include a description and link to the current tools developed under Valkyries.
- General content updates

4.1.3. Web statistics

Matomo is still the collection tool used to measure website statistics. This includes, among other things, the collection of visit counters, navigation behaviour, geographical distribution of web access and other similar features.

Figure 3 shows a graphical representation of the number of visits to the VALKYRIES website across the period covered between October 2022 (M13) and September 2023 (M24). The peak number of visits has been attained on June 23rd, 2023 with 43 visits.

Visits Over Time

Figure 3 – Website visits over time

On the other hand, the geographical distribution of visitors of the VALKYRIES website is depicted in Figure 4. Table 4 shows the 3 continents with the highest percentages of visitors. Since the

last period, the ratio of visitors per continent has increased in favour of Europe, which has the most visitors with almost 81%. The number of visitors from the USA decreased proportionally to 14%, remaining in second place, and in third place is Asia, with almost 3% of the visitors coming from that continent. It can be noted that the highest concentration of visits comes from European sources, mainly Spain (573 visits), Italy (245 visits), Greece (242 visits) and Norway (232 visits) .Within the reporting period (October 2022 – September 2023), total of **2522 visits** have been registered, accounting 8.970 page views in total.

Continent	Percentage of visitors
Europe	81%
North-America	14%
Asia	2.8%

Table 4 – Continents with the highest percentage of visits

2,522 visits

Figure 4 – Website visitors’ geographical distribution

4.2. Social media

In M2, a social media account for the project was created on LinkedIn and on Twitter. To date, VALKYRIES has presence on social media platforms progressively gaining more presence as the number of followers increases. Table 5 summarizes basic metrics of the social media platforms whereas Figure 5 and Figure 6 display the current frontmatter of the Twitter and LinkedIn accounts, respectively, adapted to the corporate identity styles defined by VALKYRIES.

Description	Twitter/X	LinkedIn	Facebook
Total number of followers	143	320	49
Entries/posts	100+	100+	20
Impressions (last 28 days)	1184	1388	141
Best Engagement rate (last 365 days)	35.1%	52.49%	68,75%

Table 5 - VALKYRIES numbers on social media platforms

Figure 5 – Twitter/X Valkyries' frontpage

Figure 6 – LinkedIn Valkyries' frontpage

Facebook has been added as the third social network. The following picture shows the front page of the new Valkyries' Facebook page.

Figure 7 - Facebook's Valkyries front page

4.3. Events participation

The list of events attended by partners of the VALKYRIES consortium, and the activities performed on each are described in Table 6.

Event Name	Country	Date	Description
XXV Jornadas Municipales sobre catástrofes	Spain	28-28 Oct. 2022	During these conferences, the VALKYRIES project presented a proposal for a testbed architecture that could be implemented in the context of the project. Some other VALKYRIES developments were presented.
CERIS	Belgium	10 Nov 2022	Valkyries was presented at CERIS – Disaster Resilient Societies cluster conference, with the title “Harmonization and Pre-standardization of equipment, training a Tactical Procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters”
Nicosia Risk Forum 2022 - CERIDES	Cyprus	15-16 Nov 2022	Next 15th-16h November took place the Nicosia Risk Forum 2022 organized by CERIDES. During this symposium, the VALKYRIES project presented.
ISMSForum	Spain	17 Nov 2022	Valkyries project coordinator was invited to speak at the 24th International Information Security Conference «Next Level Cyber Security: main actors and boardroom»
Joint-Network event From Early Warning to Action	Germany	30 Nov-2 Dec 2022	Valkyries project was invited to participate at the event with stakeholders from H2020 projects, working on all aspects of people-centred Early Warning Systems (risk knowledge, monitoring and warning service, dissemination and communication, response capability)
FEINDEF	Spain	17 May 2023	Valkyries was presented at FEINDEF as a success story. FEINDEF is the most important defence exhibition in Spain

Event Name	Country	Date	Description
25th Congress of Balkan Military Medical Committee	Bulgaria	28 th -31 st May 2023	Under the title: "Contribution of the Valkyries project to joint military-civil tactical coordinated procedures for First Aid in cross-border multi-victim disasters" Valkyries project was presented to the audience.
RISE-SD	Greece	29 th – 31 st May 2023	During the event, a detailed description of the Valkyries project was presented to the audience, including information on the first use case, a fire drill that took place in early May between the borders of Spain and Portugal.
World Maritime Rescue Congress 2023	Netherlands	18 th -20 th June 2023	The city of Rotterdam hosted the World Maritime Rescue Congress 2023, where the Valkyries project had the opportunity to present a description of the project and a poster.

Table 6 – Events attended by VALKYRIES’ partners

4.4. Press Releases

Since the execution Demos, VALKYRIES has gained attention from the general audience, present in several press releases where the aims and project envisioned capabilities have taken prominence. Evidence of the presence of VALKYRIES in the digital media can be seen in Table 7, which shows the main media contributions, including internal origin and entities external to the project, both civilian and military, that have issued press releases and small communication articles.

Source	Release Date	URL
Indra – UC1	May 2023	El proyecto europeo Valkyries, liderado por Indra, simula un incendio entre España y Portugal para mejorar la coordinación de emergencias transfronterizas indra (indracompany.com)
ABC – UC1	May 2023	https://www.abc.es/sociedad/400-efectivos-participan-simulacro-espana-portugal-20230504144807-vi.html#vca=compartirrrss&vso=abc&vmc=rrss&vli=fixed-link
OndaCero – UC1	May 2023	https://www.ondacero.es/emisoras/extremadura/noticias/mas-400-profesionales-realizan-simulacro-incendio-forestal-valencia-alcantara-portugal_202305046453cfd32a35640001f26bc0.html
UGOZapad – UC3	June 2023	https://www.ugozapad.bg/5573/obshina-sandanski-e-domakin-na-vazhno-mezhdunarodno-uchenie/
Youtube – UC3	June 2023	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-yia2upLqF0&t=2s
Sandanski – UC3	June 2023	САНДАНСКИ - ДОМАКИН НА МАЩАБНО МЕЖДУНАРОДНО УЧЕНИЕ ЗА ОКАЗВАНЕ НА ПЪРВА ПОМОЩ! - Община Сандански (sandanski.bg)
Ministry of Interior – UC2	June 2023	https://www.facebook.com/ministerstvovnutraSR https://www.instagram.com/p/Ct5py7tIJ-k/

Table 7 – VALKYRIES presence on digital media from internal and external sources

Figure 8 illustrates some examples of external media coverage attained by VALKYRIES.

The Indra-led European Valkyries project simulates a fire between Spain and Portugal to improve the coordination of cross-border emergencies

News

Events

Multimedia content

Blog Neo

Contact Press

5 May 2023 Spain

- The simulation, successfully carried out between Valencia de Alcántara in Cáceres and Marvão in Portugal, was attended by over 400 participants, including the project team, UME personnel, 112 Extremadura, Civil Protection Portugal, the Extremadura Health Service, the Red Cross and the Fire Department
- The aim was to test the standardized protocols that improve coordination in multi-victim incidents on a next-generation technology basis incorporating 5G communication, big-data based predictive analytics and Artificial Intelligence, drones and digital twins
- Indra coordinates the consortium of 17 partners, made up of emergency response organizations, companies, universities and technological centers from eight European countries within the Valkyries project funded by the H2020 innovation program

A fire with several hot spots begins in a wooded area in the province of Cáceres and spreads at high speed towards Marvão in

Община Сандански е домакин на важно международно учение

12/06/2023 16:23 Сандански

Figure 8 - Examples of VALKYRIES press releases

4.5. Communication material

In addition to the PowerPoint and Word templates that were designed following the graphic line of the project (refer to D1.9), additional communication material has been developed:

- A factsheet of the Project in triptych format (see Figure 9 right) that has the basic information about VALKYRIES and that has been distributed to more than 2000 people in several events such as the CPDP congress, the RISE-SD symposium and the ARES congress.
- A rollup to be displayed as visual appeal at conferences and events (see Figure 9 left) has also been designed and used, for example, during the VALKYRIES presentation in the RISE-SD symposium.

Figure 9 – (Left) Project rollup and (right up) front and (right down) back of the Project Factsheet in triptych format.

In addition to the previous material, some advertising elements have been generated and distributed in which the VALKYRIES logo appears, such as the pens and USB flash drives shown in Figure 10. These elements serve as an attraction for the public in those fairs in which a partner of the project has a stand with information about the project, as it was done during the Bulgarian Defence fair.

Figure 10 – Tryptic and merchandising

4.6. Newsletters

Newsletters aim to inform stakeholders about project developments and advances. At least two newsletters per year are planned to be issued on the dates indicated below:

Figure 11 – Newsletter publication

The first newsletters were published in the first period of the project. In this period, the third newsletter was published in March 2023 and the fourth in September 2023. The Consortium members are encouraged to include the VALKYRIES newsletter in their institutional newsletters and communication documents in order to increase local coverage.

5. Report on Dissemination

This section provides an overview of the progress made during the second year of project in the dissemination activities of the VALKYRIES Project. As a summary, in Table 8 we present the main actions that have been carried out between **M13 and M24** and that are part of the progress described in this section.

In the same way as with the communication strategy, in deliverable *D1.9 Communication and Dissemination Strategies* released in M6, both individual and joint dissemination strategies were defined. Likewise, a series of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were defined to measure the progress and success of these activities.

Dissemination KPIs				
Activity	Description	Expected impact	KPIs	Progress Status
VALKYRIES Workshops	VALKYRIES workshops in M6/M12/M24 will be organized.	Information exchange, dissemination; awareness.	3 workshops 30+ attendees per workshop. 25%+ of women per workshop	100%
Legal / Ethical Workshops	L/E workshops in M6/M12/M18/M24 will be organized.	Sensitize the ethical-legal framework	4 workshops 15+ attendees per workshop. 25%+ of women per workshop	100%
Standardization Workshops	workshops in M6/M12/M18/M24 will be organized.	Discussion of the VALKYRIES results on the regulation, standardization, certification and harmonization issues	4 workshops 15+ attendees per workshop. 25%+ of women per workshop	100%
Demonstration Workshops	Demonstration workshops in M6/M12/M24 will be organized	Discussion of the VALKYRIES demonstration scenarios definition, planning and execution	3 workshops 30+ attendees per workshop. 25%+ of women per workshop	100%
Liaisons	Liaisons with national and EU projects	Run liaison initiatives related with other H2020 projects to boost areas of application	5+ liaison with EU projects	100%
Publications	Scientific and high-level publications	Contribute to scientific communities, dissemination; awareness	5+ Scientific, publications with high impact 2+ Open access publications	100%
Conferences	Scientific and high-level conferences	Contribute to scientific communities, dissemination; awareness	5+ Scientific conferences with high impact	100%
Experts involved	Stakeholders committed with external advisory boards	Receive impartial scientific advice, support the PST and	5+ experts active involved per EAB	100%

Dissemination KPIs				
Activity	Description	Expected impact	KPIs	Progress Status
		advise the Consortium on social, environmental, technological, legal and economic factors that may influence the innovation management of VALKYRIES		

Table 8 - Progress in Dissemination KPIs

The activities performed in the reporting period covering M13 to M24 are described in the following subsections.

5.1. Workshops

In this section we describe the workshops organized by one or more partners of the consortium in the reporting period. These workshops correspond to those specified in Table 8. Table 9 summarizes relevant information about the workshops carried out.

Workshop	Date	Context	Location	Organizers
2 nd VALKYRIES and Demonstration	October 24 th - 25 th , 2022	Project Workshop	Virtual	Indra (IND)
2 nd Standardisation and certification	October 24 th - 25 th , 2022	Project Workshop	Virtual	Novotec (NOV), Indra (IND), USN
2 nd Legal and Ethical	October 24 th - 25 th , 2022	Computer Privacy and Data Protection (CPDP) conferences	La Cave, Brussels, Belgium	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna (SSA), Indra (IND)
3 rd Standardisation and certification	Feb 28th, 2023	Project Workshop	Virtual	Novotec (NOV), USN
3 rd Legal and Ethical	March 3rd, 2023	Project Workshop	Pisa / online	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna (SSA)
3 rd VALKYRIES and Demonstration	September 19 th , 2023	Project Workshop	Virtual	Indra (IND), SUMMA112 (SUM), ISEMI (ISE), Bulgarian Defence Institute (BDI), University of South-eastern Norway USN)
4 th Standardisation and certification	September 19 th , 2023	Project Workshop	Virtual	Novotec (NOV), USN
4 th Legal and Ethical	September 19 th , 2023	Project Workshop	Virtual	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna (SSA)

Table 9 – Relevant Workshop Information

5.1.1. 2nd VALKYRIES, Demonstration, Legal/Ethical and Standardisation & Certification Workshops

Indra (IND) organized on October 24-25th the scheduled workshops for M12 that is, 2nd VALKYRIES WS, 2nd Demonstration WS, 2nd Legal/ethical WS and 2nd Standardisation &

Certification WS. The aim of these WSs was to bring together main stakeholders of the security and emergency sectors as well as the EABs. Partners and members of the External Advisory Board participated, and the analysed gaps and opportunities were discussed, as well as the advances in the four final demonstration scenarios.

For this aim, a previous documentation about each WS was sent some days before to the EAB in order to be reviewed previous to the WSs. As well a survey has been sent to the EAB members and invited experts after the WSs development in order to collect their feedback and recommendation about the project progress.

Figure 12 – Pictures of the 2nd Valkyries workshops

5.1.2. 3rd Standardisation & Certification Workshop

Novotec (NOV) and USN organized on Feb 28th the scheduled workshop for M18 that is the 3rd Standardization WS. The aim of this WS was to bring together main stakeholders of the security and emergency sectors as well as the EABs.

The topics of the agenda included an overview about the Harmonization strategy, applied to the prioritization of chosen opportunities and sustainable international/European certification and assessment facilities.

For this aim, a previous documentation about each WS prioritized opportunities was sent some days before to the EAB in order to be reviewed previous to the WSs. As well a survey has been sent to the EAB members after the event.

Figure 13 – Pictures of the 3rd Standardisation workshops

5.1.3. 3rd Legal and Ethical Workshop

In March 2023, Sant'Anna (SSSA) hosted the 3rd VALKYRIES legal and ethical workshop, scheduled for the M18, at the Aula Magna of the Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna in Pisa.

The workshop focused on the theme, “Dealing with Ethical Legal Issues in Technology Development: Current Approaches in Projects”. During this event, important legal and ethical considerations related to the project were discussed and presented.

Additionally, the RESCUER project, which has an agreement with Valkyries, was invited and took the opportunity to share their legal and ethical findings at the workshop.

5.1.4. 3rd VALKYRIES, Demonstration and 4th Legal and Ethical, Standardisation & Certification Workshops

Indra (IND) organized on September 19th of 2023 the scheduled workshops for M24 that is, 3rd VALKYRIES WS, 3rd Demonstration WS, 4th Legal/ethical WS and 4th Standardization WS, that correspond the last Workshop of the Project.

The aim of these WSs was to present the outcomes of the project to stakeholders, making possible to better assess the impact in the invited communities and receive feedback about the planned final and post-project exploitation actions.

One of the highlights of the workshop was the presentation of the results and lessons learned from the use cases developed for UC1, UC2 and UC3, in which the different tools developed during the project were tested.

Figure 14 - 3rd VALKYRIES, Demonstration and 4th Standardization, Legal/Ethical Workshops

5.2. Scientific publications and conferences

The scientific production carried out by the VALKYRIES consortium has been divided in those published in journals and conferences.

5.2.1. Journals

The list of VALKYRIES journal publications of this reporting period is summarized in Table 10.

Title	Date of publication	of Author(s)	Journal
Comparing EU Initiatives on Data: Addressing Risks and Enhancing Harmonisation Opportunities	Jan 2023	Denise Amram	Opinion Juri
DOI: https://www.opiniojurisincomparatione.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/Amram_Online-First.pdf			

Title	Date of publication	Author(s)	Journal
Opportunities for Standardization in Emergency Scenarios in the European Union	Approved M24		International Journal of Medical Informatics
Study on the harmonization of the Minimum Data Set in the European framework for emergency services in cross-border disasters with multiple victims	Submitted M22		Plos one
A Systems-Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA) Approach. (USN)	Submitted M24		"safety science" or "Journal of Risk and Reliability"
Digitization of information and optimization of management in incidents with multiple victims. Analytical study	Submitted M24		Plos one

Table 10 – List of Journal Publications

5.2.2. Conferences and Congresses

Table 11 summarizes the list of conferences and congresses in which one or more consortium partners have made conference or poster contributions in this reporting period.

Title	Date and Country	Author(s)	Conference or congress name
A Novel Framework to Evaluate and Train Object Detection Models for Real-Time Victims Search and Rescue at Sea with Autonomous Unmanned Aerial Systems Using High-Fidelity Dynamic Marine Simulation Environment	Jan/2023 - USA	Rajeev Poudel, Luciano Lima, Fabio Andrade	WACV2023
DOI: https://openaccess.thecvf.com/content/WACV2023W/MaCVi/html/Poudel_A_Novel_Framework_To_Evaluate_and_Train_Object_Detection_Models_WACVW_2023_paper			
An Interoperable Framework for Network-Enabled Cross-Border Multi-Agency First-Aid Vehicles in Multiple Casualty Incidents	Abril/2023 - Italy	Marco Manso et al.	AllSensors
https://www.thinkmind.org/index.php?view=article&articleid=allensors_2023_2_20_70010			
Valkyries poster presented at Congress.	June 2023	HRT (Dimistris Ilianis)	World Maritime Rescue Congress 2023
Approach to harmonisation of technological solutions, operating procedures, preparedness, and cross-sectorial collaboration opportunities for first aid response in cross-border mass-casualty incidents	Aug/2023 - Italy	Yantsislav Yanakiev et al.	ARES23
https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3600160.3605060			

Table 11 – List of Conferences and Congresses

6. Liaison initiatives with other EU projects

In order to carry out a correct liaison strategy between sister European projects, the first step was to define what the consortium understood by liaison and the result was:

“The approach between two or more related European projects which lead to a synergy between them. “

The main purpose of establishing these points of contact between different EU projects is to maximize the efforts, discoveries and developments made by other consortiums trying to take advantage of previously done analysis, lessons learned, designs or even developments that enhance the results of VALKYRIES. In the same way, that the analyses and results from VALKYRIES can serve as input for other sister projects with similar topics, technologies or design decisions.

In *D1.9 Communication and Dissemination Strategies* a series of activities that could be classified as liaison activities were defined and some projects that could be possible candidates to analyse points of synergy were indicated. In this first year, we have made a series of approaches with some of these projects in which meetings and exchanges of information have been carried out to identify possible points of interest.

In order to formalize the liaison activities and establish an agreement between the coordinators of the projects involved, a formalization document has been drawn up. This document consists of a description of VALKYRIES and its sister project, the synergies and points of interest detected between them, and the list of liaison activities to be carried out. This document is then reviewed and approved by the PCs.

The projects with which Valkyries has a document liaison approved during the second period of the project M13-M24 are show on Table 12.

Project	Actions
CURSOR (Link)	(02/02/2023) CURSOR presented the project and synergies on the 4 th Valkyries Plenary. (09/03/2023) Liaison document signed.
STRATEGY (Link)	(02/02/2023) STRATEGY presented the project and synergies on the 4 th Valkyries Plenary. (15/02/2023) VALKYRIES' was invited to present the VALKYRIES strategy towards interoperability at the STRATEGY's Interoperability Workshop (01/04/2023 -) Collaboration in different deliverables. (17/07/2023) Liaison document signed.
RESCUER (Link)	(23-26/01/2023) Valkyries was invited to RESCUER drill that was hold in Navacerrada. (02/02/2023) RESCUER presented the project and synergies on the 4 th Valkyries Plenary. (22/05/2023) RESCUER presented lessons learned from drills in the 5 th Valkyries Plenary. (29/06/2023) Liaison document signed.

IProcureSecurity PCP (Link)	(28/08/2023) Valkyries and IProcureSecurity PCP started a dissemination liaison activity that continued during M24. (15/09/2023) Liaison document signed. (26/09/2023) IprocureSecurity participated in UC4 Valkyries's drill.
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Table 12 – Current status of the liaison activities with other EU projects

Below are some images of Valkyries' involvement with other projects.

Figure 15 - Valkyries at the 2nd RESCUER's pilot in Navacerrada

Figure 16 - Valkyries at the STRATEGY interoperability workshop

Figure 17 - CURSOR at the 4th Valkyries plenary meeting

Figure 18 - IprocureSecurity PCP at the 5th Valkyries Plenary meeting

7. Conclusions

This report summarizes the efforts made by the VALKYRIES consortium in its continued efforts to achieve the communication and dissemination objectives outlined in Deliverable D1.9 - Communication and Dissemination Strategies.

During this second and final year of the project, the focus has been on strengthening communication initiatives to solidify the project's identity and maintain the attention of stakeholders and experts in various emergency fields. In this context, the project website was updated and its analysis was continuously revised. In addition, VALKYRIES' presence in the media became more visible, with numerous press releases and articles aimed at the general public, especially after the Use Cases of the project. Attendance at events was also significant, with greater integration of partners' efforts to promote VALKYRIES among participants. Overall, the communication activities were carried out as planned, with satisfactory results.

In terms of dissemination activities, there was a notable output of scientific content, with publications in high-impact journals and conference presentations. These results were also presented in the second round of project workshops held at the end of M24. Finally, outreach efforts were emphasized as an integral part of the reported actions.

8. Annex A – References and bibliography

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- [4] Ukrainian-Russian war. Russian forces "are bombing critical infrastructure, " Ukraine's defense chief says., CNN News, 2022. [En línea]. Available: https://edition.cnn.com/europe/live-news/ukraine-russia-putin-news-03-05-22/h_b74ad770036da5436dd86b0095558bfc.

9. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
AES	Asociación Española de empresas de Seguridad
ARES	Availability, Reliability and Security
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
CPDP	Computer Privacy and Data Protection
DX.X	Deliverable X.X
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FR	Funding Requirement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IA	Innovation Action
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MX	Month X
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
PC	Project Coordinator
PU	Public
QX	Quartile X
R	Report
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
TX.X	Task X.X
U.S.	United States
WP	Work Package
WS	Workshops

Table 13 - Glossary